

Jismoniy tarbiya va sport gimnastikaning ahamiyati.

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Anatatsiya: Jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasidagi zamonaviy ta'lim davlat, jamiyat va shaxs darajasidagi ijtimoiy - iqtisodiy o'zgarishlar, O'zbekistonda oliy ta'limidagi sport yonalishidagi talabalarga umumevropa ta'lim makoniga kirishi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan yuqori sifatli qayta ishlashga undaydi.

Kalit so'z: Jismoniy tarbiya, gimnastika, ta'lim, kompleks jarayon, vosita mahurat.

Jismoniy tarbiya ta'limining mazmunini modernizatsiya qilish - bu kompleks jarayon bo'lib, uni amalga oshirish uni yangilash maqsadlari va qoidalarini kontseptual qayta ko'rib chiqishni, asosiy tarkibiy qismlarni muvozanatlashni, tegishli madaniy-in - shakllanish makonini yaratishni va ta'lim sifati mezonlarini ishlab chiqishni talab qiladi. Shu munosabat bilan bo'lajak mutaxassisning shaxsiga, uning kasbiy madaniyatiga bo'lgan munosabat kuchayadi.

Davlat ta'lim standarti - "jismoniy tarbiya va sport" mutaxassisligi bo'yicha "jismoniy tarbiya va sport" ixtisosligi bo'yicha maxsus pedagoglarni tayyorlashning asosiy o'quv dasturini 3 yil davomida o'zlashtirishning me'yoriy muddatini belgilaydi.

Ushbu davrda jismoniy tarbiya va sport bo'yicha mutaxassis tayyorlanganligi aniqlandi: - barcha turdagi ta'lim muassasalarida, tashkilotlarda, turli shaklidagi korxonalarda, sport turlari bo'yicha jamoaviy jamoalarda pedagogik va murabbiylik faoliyati uchun; - mahalliy, mintaqaviy va sport sohaslarida jismoniy madaniyat va sport sohasidagi boshqaruv faoliyati uchun. Federatsiyalar darajalari;

- har qanday mulkchilik shaklidagi jismoniy tarbiya va sport, sport va ko'ngilochar, sayyohlik, tibbiy, rehabilitatsiya va profilaktika muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya va sport vositalari bilan dam olish va rehabilitatsiya vazifalarini bajarish.

Jismoniy tarbiya va sport faoliyati ixtisoslashtirilgan fakultetlar talabalarining kasbiy tayyorgarligining asosiy tarkibiy qismi, formalar uchun asosdir

- kasbiy va shaxsiy muammolarni hal qilishda faollik va ijodkorlikni keltirib chiqaradigan o'zaro bog'liq va o'zaro bog'liq bo'lgan maxsus va kasbiy

- pedagogik bilim va ko'nikmalar to'plamini birlashtirish. Asosiy sport turlarini o'zlashtirish jarayonida jismoniy tarbiya va sport faoliyati mazmunini

o'zlashtirish kelajakdagi mutaxassislarning kasbiy faoliyati samaradorligining zaruriy sharti bo'lib, ularda jismoniy tarbiya va sport faoliyatining innovatsion texnologiyalarini rivojlantirishga bo'lgan ehtiyojni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bu sport fanlarining asosiy kurslarining tarkibiy tarkibi va texnologik tarkibini qayta ko'rib chiqishni talab qiladi.

Butun insoniyat olgan bilimlardan foydalanish kerak. Biz qilishimiz kerak bo'lgan asosiy narsa odamlarni sportga orgatish va sog'lomlashtirish, profesional sportga o'rganishga o'rgatishdir.

Siz doimo o'rganishingiz kerak..."

Ko'pgina ta'lim tahlilchilari, universitetlarga kiradigan maktab bitiruvchilarining ta'lim sifati pasayganligini aniq ta'kidlaydilar. Maktab bitiruvchilarining shaxsiyati va intellektual rivojlanishining sezilarli darajada kamligi.

Zamonaviy maktab o'quvchilarining sog'lig'iga etibor qaratilishi lozim bo'ladi va unga turli sport o'yinlar bevosita ko'maklashadi maktab o'quvchilarining motor faolligining etarli emasligi va maktabda jismoniy madaniyatni o'qitish sifati bilan bog'liq. Maktab jismoniy ovqatlanishining mazmuni va tuzilishi, jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining malakasi ta'lim muassasalari oldida turgan ta'lim va tarbiya muammolarini to'liq hal qilishga imkon bermaydi. Jismoniy tarbiya bo'yicha keng qamrovli dastur har doim ham to'liq qo'llanilmaydi, ayniqsa o'qituvchilar "gimnastika"bo'limini e'tiborsiz qoldiradilar.

Buning ob'ektiv va sub'ektiv sabablari bor:

- a) gimnastika mashg'ulotlarining yuqori shikastlanish xavfi;
- b) "gimnastika" bo'limida o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashning past darajasi;
- v) darsning past motor zichligi;
- d) maktablarning gimnaziya uskunalari bilan etarli darajada ta'minlanmaganligi;
- e) darsdagi jarohatlar uchun javobgar bo'lgan jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarining huquqiy xavfsizligi.

Ko'pincha, gimnastika vositalaridan foydalanmasdan, oldingi o'qituvchi jismoniy madaniyat darslarini vosita me'yorlarini o'zlashtirishga qisqartiradi, bolaning ma'lum motor fazilatlarini rivojlantirishning sezgir davrlaridan foydalanmasdan, harakatlar madaniyatini shakllantirish paytini o'tkazib yuboradi. Bundan tashqari, jismoniy tarbiya va sportga ongli munosabatni, o'quvchilarning xulq - atvor me'yorlarini shakllantirishda qiyinchiliklar mavjud. Shu munosabat bilan, universitetga kirishda abituriyentlar va talabalar gimnastika testlarini

topshirishda va "gimnastika" asosiy normativ - liniyasida dasturiy materiallarni o'zlashtirishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi.

Jismoniy tarbiya bo'yicha mutaxassisni tayyorlashda ushbu mavzuga alternativa yo'q. Jismoniy madaniyatning har tomonlama muammolarini hal qilishda uning mazmuni asosiy hisoblanadi. U beradi- amaliyot ko'rsatganidek, mahoratga erishish uchun asos bo'lib, sportning ko'p turlarida o'zining sport va amaliy ahamiyatiga ega.

Biroq, so'nggi yillarda o'quv rejalari asosiy fanlarni o'qitish soatlari hajmini umumiy muvofiqlashtirish, "maktabda gimnastika darsi", "musiqiy va ritmik ta'lim" kurslarini bekor qilish, talabalarni maktab pedagogik amaliyotiga tayyorlash shaklida aks ettirilgan. Ammo nafaqat yuqorida aytib o'tilgan sabablar ta'lim jarayonining sifatiga ta'sir qiladi, umumiy va maxsus tayyorgarlik darajasi juda past bo'lgan odamlar universitetlarga kirishlari ham muhimdir.

"Gimnastika" fanidan o'quv jarayonining sifatini oshirish maqsadida Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti universitetining jismoniy madaniyat yo'nalishi 1-3 kurs talabalari tomonidan berilgan fan bo'yicha dasturiy materiallarni o'zlashtirish sifati bo'yicha monito - ring ishlab chiqildi va o'tkazildi.

O'quv jarayonida didaktik vositalar va usullardan foydalanish pedagogik vaziyat va hal qilinadigan pedagogik vazifalar bilan bog'liq edi.

Gimnastika elementlarini o'qitish jarayoni uch bosqichni o'z ichiga oladi:

- 1) faoliyatning taxminiy asosini shakllantirish;
- 2) vosita mahoratini shakllantirish;
- 3) gimnastika bilan shug'ullanuvchilarning turmush tarsi

Jismoniy tarbiya va sport faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ikki darajada o'rganishni talab qilganligi sababli: nazariy-ratsional harakatning aqliy modelini yaratish shaklida va amaliy-harakatni amalga oshiradigan vosita mahoratini shakllantirish, o'qituvchining asosiy didaktik maqsadi o'quv jarayonini shunday qurishdir. u aqliy faoliyatga hissa qo'shadi, maqsadga muvofiqlikni o'rgatadi faoliyat, ta'lim-ixtisoslashgan hislar va hislar doirasi, o'zlashtirish uchun zarur bo'lgan jismoniy fazilatlar- gimnastika mashqlari texnikasi. Umumlashtirilgan shaklda ushbu jarayon dastlabki motivatsiya va harakatning indikativ asosini yaratishga kamayadi. Uni yaxshiroq o'zlashtirish uchun biz vosita harakatlarini tahlil qilishga va uning umumiy siqilish turlarini shakllantirishga qaratilgan "baland ovozda gapirish" dan foydalanamiz, bu esa harakatlar maktabini yaratishga yordam beradi. Bu o'quv vazifalarini bajarish usullaridan biri sifatida vosita ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga imkon berdi. Biroq, gim-nastik mashqlar texnikasini o'zlashtirish eng qiyin.

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